

Suleymaniye Mosque in Rhodes

also known as “Mosque of Süleyman Khan”, “Süleyman Khan Camii”

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Abrahamic, Greek, Aegean, Sunnism, Islam, Religious Place, Language, Turkic, Islamic Traditions, Sunni, Hanafi

The Suleymaniye Mosque in Rhodes was built shortly after the Ottoman conquest of Rhodes in 1522. The mosque is located in a central location in the walled Old Town of Rhodes, at the top of Sokratous Street, one of the main streets of the city. The mosque features a central dome over a square base, flanked by two smaller domes over square bases. It is named in honor of the Sultan Suleyman, who ruled the Ottoman Empire at the time of the conquest of Rhodes. Visiting ca. 1671, Evliya Celebi, an Ottoman traveller, described the mosque in detail. He noted that the domes were leaded, "in the style of Istanbul," as were several other mosques in the Old Town of Rhodes. The windows were decorated with "several types of glass"; the main dome was supported by marble and poryphyry columns. (Evliya, 272-273.) Notably, Evliya Celebi also writes that the entryway was decorated with "pictures of flowers and fruits"; this suggests that the current marble entryway, which matches this description, dates from before 1671. Evliya Celebi also writes that this carved door was formerly a church door. The mosque was damaged in 1856 as a result of an ammunition explosion (caused by lightning) in the nearby church of the Knights of Saint John. This led to the collapse of the minaret, which was later rebuilt. The minaret began to lean in the 1980s and was archaeologically documented before being demolished. Further restoration work on the mosque was undertaken by the Hellenic Ministry of Culture between 1998 and 2006.

Date Range: 1522 CE - 2005 CE

Region: Suleymaniye Mosque in Rhodes

Region tags: Greece

The Suleymaniye Mosque in Rhodes is located at the top of Sokratous Street, one of the central streets in the walled Old Town of Rhodes.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Evliya. Evliya Çelebi Seyahatnamesi. Translated by Seyit Ali Kahraman. Vol. 9/1. Yapı Kredi Yayınları, 2010.
- Source 2: Evliya. Evliya Çelebi, Evliya Çelebi Seyahatnamesi, Vol. IX. Translated by Yücel Dağlı, Seyit Ali Kahraman, and Robert Dankoff, 2005.

– Source 3: Dellas, Giorgios. “Süleyman Mosque.” In *Ottoman Architecture in Greece, 360–63*. Hellenic Ministry of Culture, 2008.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <http://tourism.rhodes.gr/?p=9250&lang=en>

– Source 1 Description: Information provided by the Municipality of Rhodes.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: While this site has not received excavation as such, the minaret (which had begun to lean) was documented using photogrammetry in 1988, and was later cleared due to the danger it posed (Dellas 361-363).

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1988

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Documentation was likely undertaken by the Ministry of Culture.

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Type of elevation

– Hill

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Notes: Fence

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

Notes: Currently, the mosque is a single structure; however, the current mosque was the result of joining three adjacent buildings.

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Square

Notes: The three adjacent structures, now adjoined into a single mosque, were each originally square in shape.

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

Notes: Although there is today a single mosque building, this was originally three separate

buildings that served different functions.

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
– Yes

↳ A group of features:
– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:
Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function
– Worship

↳ Worship:
– Communal
Notes: The mosque was used for both communal and individual worship.
– Individual

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed
– Collapsed

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

–Other [specify]: Not destroyed deliberately

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Human-caused accident

Notes: In 1856, lightning exploded ammunition that was kept in the nearby Saint John church (specifically, the bell tower).

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– Once

Notes: The earliest renovation seems to date from 1534 (Evliya p. 272-273).

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Monotheistic God (Allah)

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Notes: See Evliya p. 258.

Specify

– Private individual

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

Specify

– War/battle

Notes: Ottoman conquest of Rhodes

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: The mosque is located at the highest point of one of the main streets through the Old Town of Rhodes.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: Three square structures, which were originally separate, were joined to form the mosque in its current form.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The central square structure is larger than the adjoining two structures, and was the original mosque.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 100

Notes: Entry is limited to the mosque itself, and not the surrounding areas.

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 150

Notes: The central square structure is approximately 10 m by 10 m; the two adjoining square structures are approximately 5 m by 5 m. Since these three structures have been joined into a single structure, the footprint is approximately 150 square meters.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 15

Notes: See Dellas p. 360.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 150

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 15

Notes: See Dellas p. 360.

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

Notes: The minbar is made of wood. Evliya describes the mosque's minbar, along with the mihrab, as being "artistic" and "similar to those in Sinop."

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: N/A.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Glass

Notes: The windows feature glass; ca. 1671, Evliya Celebi wrote that all of the mosque's windows were "decorated with various types of glass" (p. 272-273.)

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):
– Yes

↳ On the outside:
– Yes

↳ On the inside:
– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: Stone arches

Notes: The mosque features stone arches over the exterior windows made of alternating red and white blocks.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: A supreme high god is worshipped, but is not considered to be physically present.

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ Are they sky deity:

– No

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

–Other [specify]: N/A.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Through answered prayers.

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Angels were considered to be present, and djinn may have been considered to be present.

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– No

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A.

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: 100-300

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: weekly

Notes: Large-scale rituals (Friday prayer) occurred once per week; small-scale rituals (daily prayer) occurred five times per day.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– No

↳ By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: Muslim men

Notes: Attendance to Friday prayer was optional for women.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Yes

- ↳ Priests
 - No
- ↳ Local elites
 - Yes
- ↳ Private contributions
 - No
- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: Vakf

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: Imaret

Notes: An imaret was similar to a soup kitchen, except for that it was not for the poor alone; Evliya Celebi specifies that the imaret associated with the Suleymaniye mosque had "a full table, day and night, for travelers who come and go" (Evliya 275).

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: twice annually

Notes: The major holidays, Eid ul Adha and Eid ul Fitr, both occurred once per lunar year.

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Non-Muslim members of society may not have participated in these festivals.

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: 100-300

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

- ↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:
 - Non-elites

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

- No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

- No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

- Yes

- ↳ Present full time
 - Yes

- ↳ Present part time
 - Yes

- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Male

- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:
 - No

- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:
 - No

- ↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The mosque was funded by a vakf.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Notes: The tax revenue from certain areas of land was set aside for the vakf of this mosque.

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– Yes

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– No

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– No

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: Religious specialists provided interpretation and guidance, but did not hold a monopoly over interpretation.

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– Yes

↳ Attached to the structures as decoration:

– Yes

Notes: The wooden minbar features carved Quranic passages.

↳ Housed within the place/structure:

– Yes

↳ As dedicatory inscription(s):

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A.

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Suleymaniye Mosque in Rhodes, Dellas, Giorgios. "Süleyman Mosque". In *Ottoman Architecture in Greece*, 360–63. Hellenic Ministry of Culture, 2008.

Reference: Suleymaniye Mosque in Rhodes, Evliya. Evliya Çelebi, *Evliya Çelebi Seyahatnamesi*, Vol. IX. Translated by Yücel Dağlı, Seyit Ali Kahraman, and Robert Dankoff, 2005.

Reference: Suleymaniye Mosque in Rhodes, Evliya. Evliya elebi seyahatnamesi. Translated by Seyit Ali Kahraman. Vol. 9/1. Yapı Kredi Yayınları, 2010pp. 257-274.